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D1.1 Data Management Plan

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Revision History

Abstract

Project Data Management Plan

Version	Date	Changes made	Author(s)
1.0	09.09.2025	First version	Robin Navest (LYG)
1.1	14.10.2025	Minor content updates and conversion to CANDLE template	Robin Navest (LYG)
1.2	07.11.2025	Update after internal review	Robin Navest (LYG)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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List of Abbreviations

CSA — Coordination and Support Action	HDAB — Health Data Access Body
DAAM — Data Access Application Management	NCDN — National Cancer Data Node
ECPDC— European Cancer Patient Digital Centre	SOP — Standard Operating Procedure
EHDS — European Health Data Space	SPE — Secure Processing environment
GDPR — General Data Protection Regulation	UNCAN — UNderstanding CANcer

1 Project

The data and work described in this DMP are applicable to the National Cancer data Node Developers project

Acronym

CANDLE

Start date

2025-06-02

End date

2028-05-31

Funding

- **European Health and Digital Executive Agency** (European Union): HORIZON-MISS-2024-CANCER-01 (granted)

Despite decades of devoted research, cancer remains a tremendous health threat and societal burden. Europe's Beating Cancer Plan aims to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 by improving prevention, early detection, diagnostics, therapeutics, and quality of life. The biggest single hurdle here is the highly inadequate way cancer data, both from research and healthcare, are still being dealt with. While other areas of society (e.g. e-finance, e-commerce, logistics, travel, meteorology, etc.) have fully exploited advances in data and information technology to serve organisations as well as individual consumers, so far this has failed in the health domain. Consequently, cancer data are hard to Find, Access, make Interoperable and Reuse. Evidently this is not caused by lack of suitable technology, but rather by organisational, social and cultural causes. Inherently, solving the problem requires a cultural shift from the current craftsmanship approach to cancer research and data, to a drastic collaboration model at industrial scale. CANDLE therefore aims to scale-up and improve existing (inter)national health data infrastructures, align maximally with national European Health Data Space (EHDS) implementations in member states, including HDABs, DAAMSs and SPEs. This will support European member states and associated countries in establishing a National Cancer Data Node (NCDN). Additionally, CANDLE will identify and resolve potential barriers that jeopardize effective implementation of UNCAN.eu, a federated European cancer research data infrastructure, and ECPDC, a European network of national digital infrastructures for cancer patients, platforms. CANDLE aims to equip data users and NCDN developers with a 'ready-to-use' CANDLE Resource Kit in a process-oriented (research journey, patient journey, data life cycle) way. This action is part of the Cancer Mission clusters of projects 'Understanding' and 'Quality of Life' established in 2022 and 2023. In summary, CANDLE will provide an avenue towards a successful and highly desired data transformation in European cancer research and serve as a catalyzer for the UNCAN.eu and ECPDC platforms by advancing the development of NCDNs to reach the goal of the Cancer Mission and Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, i.e. reducing the burden of cancer.

2 Data Summary

CANDLE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and therefore data generation and further processing will be limited. We will be using the following data formats and types:

- Administrative data (e.g. contact details) for the execution of the project.
- Survey data to collect input from experts on specific topics.

A standardized format will be used. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

No research data will be generated or (re)used in the project.

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We will use version history on the project SharePoint to make sure that there is adequate provenance of the data.

We made an SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) for file naming. This is defined in the project management handbook.

3.2 Making data accessible

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

The data cannot become completely open because of:

- Administrative data (e.g. contact details) is personal data and does not contribute to open science.
- Survey data might contain personal data

For the authorization of potential users, Lygature will take care of authorization of potential users of the project SharePoint.

Our data is legally not copyrightable, there is no legal owner.

3.3 Making data interoperable

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- Administrative data (e.g. contact details)
- Survey data

3.4 Increase data re-use

As explained in Section 3.2, our data cannot become completely open, but also has no IP restrictions.

The administrative data is personal data but not belonging to one of the specifically sensitive categories listed in the GDPR. The data is only needed for project administration by the project management team; further pseudonymization, anonymization or aggregation is therefore not needed nor useful. We do not plan to be archiving data (using so-called *cold storage*) for long term preservation already during the project.

The survey data might contain personal data (e.g. contact details) not belonging to one of the specifically sensitive categories listed in the GDPR. The data is only needed for the co-creation of the NCDNs by the relevant work package members; aggregation of results might be performed to share the results outside of the consortium. We do not plan to be archiving data (using so-called *cold storage*) for long term preservation already during the project.

4 Other research outputs

We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard for planning our data management and creating this DMP. The management and planning of other research outputs is done separately and is included as an [appendix](#) to this DMP. Still, we benefit from data stewardship guidance (e.g. FAIR principles, openness, or security) and it is reflected in our plans with respect to other research outputs.

5 Allocation of resources

FAIR is a central part of our data management; it is considered at every decision in our data management plan. We use the FAIR data process ourselves to make our use of the data as efficient as possible.

Robin Navest and Ummi Ciptasari are responsible for reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing the administrative data on SharePoint.

The relevant WP leads are responsible for the survey data.

Robin Navest and Ummi Ciptasari are responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

6 Data security

Project members will not store personal health data on the project SharePoint. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project. Personal (administrative) data is stored in a separate area of SharePoint which is only accessible by authorized members of the project management team.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

We are running the project in collaboration between different groups and institutes. A consortium agreement that describes who can have access to what data in the project is set.

7 Ethics

7.1 Data we collect

We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. "personal data". We explored GDPR considerations and relevant materials. We use a different legal base for collection of personal data rather than public interest or consent-based: to fulfil a contract. The purpose of processing the personal data can be described as follows: Project management activities within the CANDLE project.

The data collection is not subject to ethical legislation.

8 Other issues

We use the [Data Stewardship Wizard](https://researchers.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard) with its *Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: dsw:root:2.6.12) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://researchers.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard> DSW instance where the project has direct URL: <https://researchers.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard/projects/4373ae20-0eee-4c13-a145-30c665403f2e>.

We will be using the following policies and procedures for data management:

- **Horizon Europe DMP template**
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

Appendix: other research outputs

None to report currently.